

TODAY'S YOUTH: FUTURE CORNERSTONES

Krishna Dere¹

¹Department of Pediatric and Preventive Dentistry, College of Dental Sciences and Research Centre, Ahmedabad, India

EDITORIAL

ABSTRACT

An editorial piece that focuses on a crucial aspect of education, emphasizing on the mental toughness that is expected from the dental surgeons of tomorrow.

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As the Gen Z approaches youth, we have encountered a new wave of people who believe in outcome equality. They believe their intrinsic value as being equal to anyone else; regardless of talent, hard work or skill. Close observation makes us realize that patience and tolerance level is decreasing. There is a sharp increase in short temperedness. Unfortunately, the nurturing of the present generation has been care-free. This is making them blissfully unaware of their ignorance and incompetence.

The youth today don't even realize their actions and have no guilt about their outcomes. Why do some people in this generation lose their patience quickly? Why are they depressed and have FOMO (fear of missing out)? Knowing the reason can help us to deal with these people whom we encounter and meet every day.

Reasons can be attributed to the influence of social media, OTT platforms for kids and young adults (especially after the Covid-19 pandemic) and online education. They are more engrossed in the world of internet and are negatively influenced by their colleagues and peers. A lot of young blood wants to appear happy and try to get noticed on social media. They are running an endless race of showing their 'cooler' side to please people. But are they satisfied with what they are doing or simply swimming in the unsteady flow of their peers? If they don't get the expected response, the result will be a population of depressed and anxious people. They lack focus and concentration.

Parenting also plays a pivotal role on this subject. When things are made available to children easily, they don't value them. This makes them uninitiated to morals. They are not scolded or punished for their wrong or unethical actions.

Constant pressure, unhealthy competition with peers and self-boasting is not uncommon. It can lead to loss of confidence, tolerance and empathy in the youth. Inevitable factors of genetics and systemic conditions might not be under our control. But humanistic factors of stress, inherent nature and home environment also add to this social dilemma.

In the present scenario, young people represent the society and nation. They are being transformed consciously or not at school, university or at work place. They have vision, new knowledge, attitude to do something unique and innovative. They are full of new energy and productivity. The only shortcoming is that they need guidance on how to channel their energy into something productive.

As a guide or mentor, we can be a role model and can inspire and shape students and younger ones. They need encouragement for more physical activity and outdoor adventures. A positive mental and physical health is paramount in today's era. Additionally, the youth need to focus on the importance of keeping themselves busy. We as mentors can mould them into more empathetic and compassionate persons.

"The future promise of any nation can be directly measured by the present prospects of its youth." - John F. Kennedy